

SURVEILLANCE CARD RIFT VALLEY FEVER (RVF)- Indicator-based surveillance of abortion and increased mortality in young stock in ruminants

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Indicator-based surveillance of abortions and increased mortality in young stock in all domestic ruminants, followed by antigen testing for Rift Valley Fever Virus in farms with high incidence.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen.
3	Target species and group	Cattle, sheep and goats with clinical signs.
4	Target sector / production type	All production types (dairy / meat / wool production).
5	Geographical area covered	Whole area of EU.
6	Age group	Focus on young stock (mortality) and reproducing females (abortions).
7	Sampling point and strategy	On farm, indicator-based surveillance of the whole population followed by sampling of herds based on the incidence of clinical signs.
8	Sampling time period	Year-round, focus on high-risk period (summer and autumn) possible.
9	Sampling matrix	Tissue and blood from dead animals and aborted fetuses.
10	Type of disease indicators	Virus detection.
11	Sampling unit	Individual animal.
12	Allocation of animal groups / animals to sampling	Active sampling of animals in farms with a high incidence of mortality and abortions. High incidence could be defined uniformly for all countries, or according to reference values of specific production sectors.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Submission of tissues from dead animals and aborted fetuses (according to specifications of reference laboratory). Testing of samples with RT-PCR for RVFV.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population

15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	If disease awareness is high, sensitivity of the surveillance component to detect disease introduction within a few months can be close to 100% for a strain which causes severe clinical signs.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Q-Fever, Brucellosis, Infectious Bovine Rhinotracheitis, Chlamydiosis (and many other pathogens causing abortions).
18	References	1) https://www.woah.org/en/disease/rift-valley-fever/ 2) Jeffrey Mariner. 2018. Rift Valley Fever Surveillance. FAO Animal Production and Health Manual No. 21. Rome. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). 80 pages.
19	Additional comments	The surveillance in animals should be accompanied by a matched surveillance in humans. For example, farmers of affected farms could be tested for antibodies to RVF.